

EDUCATION OF FUTURE PRESCHOOL TEACHERS IN A MODERN SPIRIT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7870754>

Annotatsiya Farzand tarbiyasi aslida ikki so'zdan iborat. Shuning uchun ham nazaringizda juda mayda muoammodek ko'rinadi. Lekin dono odamlar biladilarki, Odamning siyosiy, diniy, ijmoiy inqiloblarining asosi ana shu ikki so'z-bola tarbiyasi dan iborat birikmaga bog'liq. Bu xalqning harakat qilishi davlatmand bo'lishi, baxli bo'lib izzat-hurmat topishi, jahongiz bo'lishi, zaif bo'lib xorlikka tushishi, faqirlik kiyimini kiyib baxtsizlik yukini tortib e'tibordan qolishi, o'zgalarga tobe, qul va asir bo'lishi, bolalikdan o'z ota-onalaridan olgan tarbiyalariga bog'liq **Kalit so'z** ta'lim, tarbiya, jamiyat, metadist, mohorat, kasb, malaka, rahbar, zamonaviy tarbiyachi

Аннотация: Абстрактное воспитание на самом деле состоит из двух слов. Вот почему это кажется вам очень маленькой проблемой. Но мудрые люди знают, что в основе политических, религиозных и социальных революций Адама лежит сочетание этих двух слов и детского воспитания. Действие этого народа состоит в том, чтобы стать государственным деятелем, быть уважаемым, будучи жадным, гордиться, быть униженным, будучи слабым, быть проигнорированным, нося одежду бедности и неся бремя несчастья, подчиняться другим, рабов и пленников. зависит от воспитания, полученного ими от родителей с детства

Ключевые слова образование, воспитание, общество, металлист, мастерство, профессия, квалификация, лидер, современный педагог

Abstract Parenting actually consists of two words. That's why it seems like a very small problem to you. But wise people know that the basis of political, religious and social revolutions of Adam depends on the combination of these two words and child education. The action of this people is to become a statesman, to be respected by being greedy, to be proud, to be humbled by being weak, to be ignored by wearing the clothes of poverty and carrying the burden of misfortune, to be subordinate to others, slaves and captives. depends on the education they received from their parents since childhood

Keywords education. upbringing, society, metadist, skill, profession, qualification, leader, modern educator

The success of the huge reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan depends first of all on people's responsibility towards their work, their ability to do meritorious work that contributes to the development of the country in their daily work. In the society, the pedagogue (teacher, educator) performs honorable and responsible tasks, firstly, to educate the growing generation, and secondly, to provide all-round knowledge to our hardworking people. The greatest duty of an educator is to train intelligent, capable, and well-educated students who will benefit the people.

The political maturity of an educator helps to realize his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of children's education, to creatively approach the solution of

educational and educational tasks, to constantly activate his skills and to help his colleagues grow at work. An educator should know the life of the country where he lives, understand the factors of nature and society, and be socially active. "Methodist teacher", "senior teacher", "Methodist educator", "People's they are awarded with "excellence of education" and similar honorary titles. With the initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, the monthly salaries of teachers in our country are increasing year by year, and their living conditions are improving. Scientific-methodological centers for training of teaching staff are being expanded, the demand for their political training is increasing, conditions are being created for them to undergo retraining every 4-5 years. It is known that the educational process in educational institutions is organized and conducted directly by the teacher. A child's attitude to educational activities is determined more by his attitude to the educator. Achieving the goals of education in the new social conditions, organizing various educational activities of students in and out of class, raising them to be knowledgeable, polite, faithful, patriotic, hardworking, well-rounded people and to the profession guidance is entrusted to teachers. Today, educators are professionals who take care of the children of the people as if they were their own children and also carry out education and upbringing at the same time. The educator creates good conditions for the physical development of each child in his group, for his higher nervous activity to work well, as well as for normal upbringing from the mental, moral, labor, and aesthetic aspects. The educator, knowing well the unique characteristics of each child, gradually loses the unique characteristics (if harmful) and makes comfortable demands on the child. The educator should be a mother, a kind teacher, a psychologist. . Among the professions, the teacher's profession is one of the most demanding and at the same time honorable professions.[2]

The teacher should be able to look at many students with one eye during the day, listen to their wishes, understand the children's whims, their habits, and their characters. An educator embodies observant, entertaining, attentive, patient, organizing, and caring features. An educator should develop qualities and opportunities that will help each child to become a real person in the future. In the period of preschool education, the teacher's personal influence on the child is very great. Because every impression of this period will remain in the child's memory for a lifetime.

Being able to understand the child and enter his spiritual world requires excellent professional training from the educator. A lively relationship with a child is a source of ideas, pedagogical innovations, joys and worries, without which the creative work of an educator cannot be imagined. During the day, the educator gets into wonderful situations with many children. Educating parents also face objections from the authorities, which are often unjustified. That's why we, parents and leaders, should listen to the feelings of the educator. Listen to his thoughts and consult with teachers.

Educators lovingly educate children with hearts as pure as white paper. They bring up children in the spirit of respect for the country, family, parents, honesty, honesty, friendship, and humanitarianism. Preschool children try to put themselves above other children. Sometimes he likes the fact that his parents are busy with their profession. In this case, it is necessary to work with the children's parents, to understand with specific examples about the necessity and importance of each profession. If children manage to do some things and belittle others, the teacher should tell the child that it is not appropriate to praise oneself, that one should teach something to a friend who does not know something.

The educator should not use the words "I don't want to see you" or "I will transfer you to another group" to rowdy children. On the contrary, it is necessary to explain to the child with sweet words. In order to prevent these situations from occurring, our educators must be highly skilled. We believe that our modern educators are highly motivated.

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